

UZBEK LANGUAGE AND ITS TERMINOLOGY

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Abstract. The article comprehensively covers the history of the formation of Uzbek language terminology as a branch of linguistics. The development and enrichment of Uzbek language vocabulary and terminology and perspectives on their evolution are analyzed.

Keywords: language, linguistics, vocabulary, term, terminology, professionalism.

УЗБЕКСКИЙ ЯЗЫК И ЕГО ТЕРМИНОЛОГИЯ

Аннотация. В статье всесторонне освещается история формирования терминологии узбекского языка как раздела языкознания. Анализируются развитие и обогащение лексики и терминологии узбекского языка, перспективы их эволюции.

Ключевые слова: язык, языкознание, лексика, термин, терминология, профессионализм.

Language is a complex communication system or the ability to study and use this system, serves as the primary object of study in linguistics. As an inseparable part of its vocabulary, the terminology of the Uzbek language develops and enriches alongside the general lexicon, reflecting all processes in the evolution of society and language.

Terminology is a branch of vocabulary related to a specific field of science, technology, industry, art, culture, sports, or social activity, representing a system of concepts and terms. It is a field of linguistics that studies terms.

In all works dedicated to terminology, a term is considered a unit that carries a definition representing a specific concept in each field and primarily performs a nominative function.

A. Reformatsky, while defining a term, concludes that "terms are special words." A.V. Kalinin refers to words used in specific sciences and professions as "special vocabulary" and divides them into two groups: terms and professionalisms. He further explains, "The difference between a term and a professionalism is that a term is the official, accepted, and standardized name of a concept in a specific field of science, art, agriculture, or technology, while a professionalism is a semi-official word commonly used in colloquial language within a profession or specialty."

Terminology has always been one of the pressing issues in linguistics, as defining the role and function of terms in the lexical layers of various fields allows for a proper understanding of the essence of concepts.

In global linguistics, scholars such as B.N. Golovin, A.V. Kalinin, V.P. Danilenko, L.I. Bozhno, and D.S. Lotte, and in Russian linguistics, V.V. Vinogradov, have extensively researched the field of terminology.

Uzbek language terminology has undergone significant development. The work in this field was initially managed by the Committee on Language and Terminology under the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the Uzbek SSR in the 1950s (active from 1931 to 1937).

Later, the Terminology Department under the Institute of Language and Literature of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan (established in 1964) took over. In 1977, Renat Doniyorov's book "Some Issues of Uzbek Technical Terminology" was published, followed by a major work titled "Lexicology of the Uzbek Language" by a group of linguists from the Institute of Language and Literature in 1981. The Republican Committee on Terminology under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan worked on regulating and improving Uzbek terminology from 1988 to 2004 (its activities were halted in January 2004).

In the comprehensive study of Uzbek terminology, the contributions of scholars such as R. Doniyorov, D.Kh. Bazarova, K. Sharipova, U. Tursunov, Kh. Dadaboyev, and K.M. Musayev are invaluable. K.M. Musayev's views on Uzbek terminology remain highly relevant in modern linguistics. He compares terminology to a city, suggesting that while it is built on a unified plan, it is not constructed all at once. It evolves under historical conditions, with contributions from various generations of architects, designers, and innovators. Each structure is carefully studied before being built, which explains the unique complexity of regulating terminology.

Terminology has its own distinct characteristics. For example, while synonymy, homonymy, and polysemy are considered enrichments in general literary language, they are viewed negatively in terminology. For instance, the term "semiconductor" cannot be replaced with words like "partial conductor" or "half conductor," as this would complicate the processes of reading, teaching, and information exchange. Therefore, in all languages with a stable level of terminology, terms are constantly regulated. This regulation is based on specific terminological standards. The publication of specialized dictionaries for various scientific fields also plays a crucial role in the development of terminology.

The development and enrichment of terminology occur in various ways. The enrichment of Uzbek terminology primarily happens through borrowing from other languages and internal word formation. The stability of a terminological system in any field is determined by its regulation and consistency.

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